

Water quality assessment of the Banong River receiving effluent from Sleman Public Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Hospital effluent has the potential to release both chemical substances and pathogenic microorganisms into surrounding water bodies, creating hazards for the environment and human health. There is a scarcity of studies in Indonesia that assess the impact of hospital wastewater on river ecosystems using benchmark regulations. This study measured the quality of wastewater at a point 50 meters before discharge and 50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant by analyzing six main parameters of temperature, potential of hydrogen (pH), Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total dissolved solids (TDS), and total suspended solids (TSS), then compared with the water quality standards according to the Regulation of the Governor of the Special Region of Yogyakarta No. 20/2008. This study found that although temperature and pH remained within acceptable ranges, higher BOD, COD, and TDS levels downstream indicated that hospital wastewater was adding to the river's organic and chemical pollution. Improved wastewater treatment processes and consistent monitoring are essential to protect ecosystem integrity and public health.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are recognized as significant sources of wastewater and solid waste due to the wide range of medical services and activities they perform. Studies indicate that high-income countries tend to produce larger volumes of wastewater compared to upper and lower-middle-income nations. In contrast, the latter generate greater amounts of biomedical waste (BMW) than their high-income counterparts [1].

The relationship between solid waste disposal methods and water quality indicates that inadequate waste management practices negatively affect the water quality in the study area [2]. The sewage discharge reveals the occurrence of heavy metals in hospital wastewater, even though it does not reveal a high concentration [3]. This study demonstrates that waste disposal sites contribute to the deterioration of surface water quality by altering its physicochemical properties and increasing pollution indicators [4].

Typically, hospital effluents contain diverse physicochemical, biological, nutrient, and organic contaminants, which may pose environmental and public health risks [1]. The main parameters that affect the water quality were potential of hydrogen (pH), temperature, turbidity, total suspended solids (TSS), DO, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), N-NH₄⁺, P-PO₄³⁻, Fe, and As [5].

Although some parameters remain within permissible limits, the elevated turbidity and BOD values highlight a clear risk of long-term environmental degradation [4].

Sources of pollution significantly affect water quality indicators, with certain sites showing strong impacts from sewage discharge and industrial wastewater effluents [6]. This infectious wastewater potentially leads to environmental disturbances to the rivers and oceans [7]. Assessing and mapping the various determinants affecting hospital liquid medical waste management is very important [8]. There is a scarcity of studies in Indonesia that assess the impact of hospital wastewater on river ecosystems using benchmark regulations. Given these concerns, monitoring and managing wastewater discharges into receiving water bodies is essential to safeguard environmental and public health. This study therefore focuses on assessing the water quality of the Banong River as the recipient of effluent from the Sleman Public Hospital wastewater treatment plant.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design to describe the water quality of the Banong River, which serves as a receiving water body for the effluent discharged from the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) of Sleman Regional Public Hospital located in Morangan, Triharjo, Sleman, Yogyakarta Special Region. The research aimed to assess the degree of pollution in the river by analyzing laboratory test results for six key parameters: temperature, pH, BOD, COD, total dissolved solids (TDS), and TSS. The values obtained were then compared against the provincial water quality standards stipulated in Governor Regulation of the Special Region of Yogyakarta No. 20/2008 [9].

2.2. Water sampling technique, location, and period

Water samples were collected using the grab sampling method at two points. Sampling was conducted 50 meters upstream to represent baseline conditions unaffected by effluent and 50 meters downstream to measure the direct impact of the WWTP discharge within the river's mixing zone. The study was conducted along the Banong River in Morangan, Triharjo Village, Sleman Regency, Yogyakarta, from April 2019 to October 2020, during which two sampling events per year were carried out to capture seasonal variations and ensure more reliable and representative water quality data at a location that directly receives effluent from the hospital's WWTP.

2.3. Parameters analyzed and data analysis

The parameters analyzed in this study included:

- a) Temperature (°C) test method Indonesian national standards (SNI) 06-6989.23-2005
- b) pH SNI (Indonesian national standards) 06-6989.11-2019
- c) Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD, mg/L) Indonesian national standards (SNI) 6989.72-2009
- d) Chemical oxygen demand (COD, mg/L) Indonesian national standards (SNI) 6989.2-2019
- e) Total suspended solids (TSS, mg/L) Indonesian national standards (SNI) 06-6989.3-2004 gravimetric method
- f) Total dissolved solids (TDS, mg/L) Indonesian national standards (SNI) 06-6989.3-2004 gravimetric method

Measurements were conducted by the Yogyakarta Regional Public Health Laboratory, analyzed using descriptive statistics, and compared with Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008, with parameter values evaluated against threshold standards, upstream–downstream variations assessed, and, where relevant, a pollution index (PI) calculated to classify water pollution levels in the Banong River.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Temperature

The observation and measurement results of the wastewater temperature parameter from the Sleman Public Hospital WWTP, using the SNI 06-6989.23-2005 testing method, are presented in Table 1. Table 1: The wastewater temperature measurements showed relatively high values compared with the limits set by the governor's regulation. This condition is likely due to the open storage tank being exposed to direct sunlight, which can increase the water temperature. In many cases, healthcare facilities release emerging contaminants (ECs) and microorganisms directly into aquatic environments without adequate treatment, posing significant risks to both environmental health and ecosystem sustainability [10]. The release of untreated effluent into surface waters represents a major risk to both environmental integrity and human health [11]. Using domestic wastewater treatment plants for hospital effluents is not recommended, as conventional systems are unable to

effectively remove many of the unique contaminants present in hospital wastewater [12]. Considering the complex nature of hospital wastewater and its potential to trigger disease outbreaks, rigorous monitoring and proper treatment are essential to avoid adverse social and environmental impacts. The results of this study indicate that most of the discharged effluent parameters did not comply with established discharge standards [13]. The temperature at both upstream and downstream points of the Banong River remained stable at 25-26 °C across the four sampling periods, with no difference observed between the two locations. These findings indicate that the WWTP effluent from Sleman Public Hospital does not cause thermal pollution, as all values were within the permissible limits of the water quality standard.

Table 1. Results of the wastewater temperature parameter

No	Date	Sampling points		Mean	Quality standards Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008, Class II water bodies
		50 meters before the wastewater treatment plant outlet	50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant outlet		
1	April 11, 2019	26 °C	26 °C	26 °C	Air temperature ± 3 °C
2	October 1, 2019	26 °C	26 °C	26 °C	
3	May 4, 2020	26 °C	26 °C	26 °C	
4	October 6, 2020	25 °C	25 °C	25 °C	

Source: Primary data

3.2. pH

The observation and measurement results of the acidity pH parameter of the Banong River water, using the SNI 06-6989.11-2019 method, are presented in Table 2. Table 2 shows that the pH measurement results can be considered stable, as they are still within the regulatory range. This is possible due to the temperature being higher than the water's pH. Many pharmaceuticals possess low lipophilicity, making them difficult to eliminate during wastewater treatment. Without proper regulation, their concentrations may surpass the predicted no-effect levels, posing significant risks to both environmental and public health [14]. The direct release of untreated sewage into receiving water bodies contributes significantly to water pollution problems [15]. Greater attention must be directed toward hospital wastewater management, beginning with treatment plant design, due to the high pollution load contained in hospital effluents [16]. Inadequate wastewater treatment may lead to various problems, such as foul odors and increased risks to public health [17]. Discharging this effluent into aquatic environments impacts crucial water quality indicators, such as biochemical BOD, COD, TDS, TSS, and pH [18]. The pH levels in the Banong River consistently meet the water quality requirements for Class II surface waters as defined by Governor Regulation of Yogyakarta No. 20/2008. The data demonstrate that the effluent from Sleman Public Hospital WWTP does not adversely impact the river's pH balance, and the aquatic environment remains within safe limits for both ecological and public health concerns.

Table 2. Measurement results of the acidity pH parameter

No	Date	Sampling points		Mean	Quality standards Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008 Class II Water Bodies
		50 meters before the wastewater treatment plant outlet	50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant outlet		
1	April 11, 2019	7.6	7.5	7.55	6.0 – 8.5
2	October 1, 2019	7.1	7.4	7.25	
3	May 4, 2020	7.7	7.8	77.5	
4	October 6, 2020	7.5	7.6	75.5	

Source: Primary data

3.3. BOD

The observation and measurement results of the BOD parameter defined as the amount of dissolved oxygen required by microorganisms to decompose organic matter under aerobic conditions in the Banong River, using the SNI 6989.72-2009 testing method, are presented in Table 3. Table 3 shows that the highest BOD value of 4.8 was recorded in October 2019 at the point 50 meters downstream of the discharge outlet, likely due to an increased loading from the wastewater treatment plant. Hospital wastewater poses a significant environmental and public health challenge because it serves as a source of both chemical and microbiological contamination [19]. The results indicate that certain physical and chemical parameters of Belik River water, specifically TSS and BOD, exceeded the Class II Water Quality Standards (WQS), while the remaining parameters were within acceptable limits [20]. The polluted areas should be treated to restore

their ecological functions [21]. High concentrations of harmful bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, *Acinetobacter*, *Enterococcus*, *Streptococcus*, and *Pseudomonas*, have been detected in untreated hospital wastewater [22]. The rigorous application of suitable disinfection technologies for hospital wastewater can significantly lower the bacterial load entering urban treatment plants, thereby reducing the spread of resistant pathogens into the environment [23]. The BOD concentrations in the Banong River generally comply with the quality standard for Class II surface waters, except for a single instance in October 2019. This anomaly suggests the possibility of periodic fluctuations in the WWTP's efficiency or changes in influent characteristics. While the river shows resilience in recovering BOD levels shortly afterward, periodic monitoring and evaluation of WWTP performance are recommended to ensure consistent compliance and protect aquatic ecosystems and public health.

Table 3. Measurement results of the BOD parameter

No	Date	Sampling points		Mean	Quality standards Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008 Class II Water Bodies
		50 meters before the wastewater treatment plant outlet	50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant outlet		
1	April 11, 2019	1.1	1.9	1.5	3 mg/L
2	October 1, 2019	1.6	4.8	2.7	
3	May 4, 2020	2.6	2.7	2.65	
4	October 6, 2020	3.0	2.6	2.8	

Source: Primary data

3.4. COD

The COD parameter represents the amount of oxygen required for the chemical decomposition of organic matter in water. High COD levels can reduce the concentration of dissolved oxygen, which may negatively affect aquatic ecosystems. The measurement results of the COD parameter in the Banong River, tested using the SNI 6989.2-2019 method, are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Measurement results of the COD parameter

No	Date	Sampling points		Mean	Quality standards Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008 Class II Water Bodies
		50 meters before the wastewater treatment plant outlet	50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant outlet		
1	April 11, 2019	4.7	14.3	9.5	25 mg/L
2	October 1, 2019	5.0	15.4	10.2	
3	May 4, 2020	25.7	27.6	26.65	
4	October 6, 2020	29.5	24.2	26.85	

Source: Primary data

Table 4 shows the COD measurements, a significant increase from 2019 to 2020, with an average value of 26, which was likely associated with the rise in COVID-19 patients that contributed to higher volumes and loads of generated wastewater. A sewage treatment plant is also the key point where surface water receives toxic residues [24]. Chemical components in natural water bodies interact within the environment in much more complex ways compared to when they are studied in isolation [25]. The widespread detection of various pharmaceutical compounds in water sources presents risks to both ecosystems and human health, highlighting the urgent need for effective and sustainable remediation approaches [26]. Water treatment is an essential process required before water can be utilized for various purposes, and the chosen technology must be both effective and carefully evaluated from multiple perspectives [27]. Wastewater discharged from four selected PPIs contained high levels of pollutants and heavy metals, indicating the need for tertiary treatment before environmental release [28]. The COD levels in the Banong River generally comply with water quality standards but showed exceedances in mid and late 2020, both upstream and downstream. This suggests that not only the WWTP discharge but also other upstream sources or reduced river self-purification capacity may be contributing to organic/inorganic pollution. The findings highlight the need for integrated catchment-based monitoring and for the WWTP to maintain consistent treatment efficiency, particularly during periods of environmental stress or increased pollutant load.

3.5. TSS

The observation and measurement results of the TSS parameter of the Banong River, using the SNI 06-6989.3-2004 gravimetric method, are presented in Table 5. Table 5 shows that the TSS measurement

results can be considered stable and remain below the allowable quality standards set by the governor's regulation. This condition is likely due to the filtration process in the wastewater treatment system, which effectively removes small particles before the effluent is discharged into the Banong River. Inadequate wastewater management can lead to residual antibiotics persisting in surface waters, thereby heightening the risk of contaminant exposure [29]. Improper solid waste management and the discharge of untreated wastewater in and around the study area contribute to heavy metal contamination [30]. Targeted measures are necessary to eliminate these metals before wastewater is released into the surrounding environment [31]. The data suggest that the effluent from the Sleman Public Hospital WWTP does not significantly increase the TSS levels in the Banong River. All values remained far below the maximum threshold specified by local water quality standards. Therefore, based on TSS measurements, the impact of hospital wastewater discharge on river sediment load is negligible, and the water body remains within acceptable environmental and public health safety limits.

Table 5. Measurement results of the TSS parameter

No	Date	Sampling points		Mean	Quality standards Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008 Class II Water Bodies
		50 meters before the wastewater treatment plant outlet	50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant outlet		
1	April 11, 2019	5	4	4.5	
2	October 1, 2019	7	6	6.5	50 mg/L
3	May 4, 2020	3	6	4.5	
4	October 6, 2020	5	4	4.5	

Source: Primary data

3.6. TDS

The observation and measurement results of the TDS parameter of the Banong River, using the SNI 06-6989.3-2004 gravimetric method, are presented in Table 6. Table 6 shows the TDS parameter measurements, that it is still far below the threshold permitted by the governor's regulations. This is likely due to the high level of diluent in the wastewater, which could originate from sanitation, air conditioning wastewater, and laundry wastewater. The hospital effluents comprise an array of toxic environmental contaminants [32]. Globally, nearly 80% of untreated wastewater is discharged into the environment, contaminating natural ecosystems. The nitrogen and phosphorus it contains disturb aquatic life and cause considerable ecological harm [15]. To safeguard river ecosystems and public health, it is essential for authorities to promptly identify and regulate heavy metal pollution sources, including industrial discharges and agricultural runoff, while enforcing stricter monitoring of water quality and food safety [33]. Wastewater treatment techniques should be adapted to remove organic micro-contaminants from wastewater [34]. Ongoing monitoring of heavy metal levels in both environmental media and living organisms is crucial to ensure long-term protection of ecosystems and public health [35]. The TDS concentrations in the Banong River following the discharge from the Sleman Public Hospital wastewater treatment facility are consistently within the permissible limits as set by Governor Regulation of Yogyakarta No. 20/2008 for Class II waters. Although there is a measurable increase in TDS downstream most notably in October 2019 the levels remain well under the regulatory threshold. These results indicate that the effluent does not significantly degrade water quality in terms of dissolved solids, and the river remains environmentally safe and compliant with public health standards.

Table 6. Measurement results of the TDS parameter

No	Date	Sampling points		Mean	Quality Standards Yogyakarta Governor Regulation No. 20/2008 Class II Water Bodies
		50 meters before the wastewater treatment plant outlet	50 meters after the wastewater treatment plant outlet		
1	April 11, 2019	103	109	104.5	
2	October 1, 2019	126	376	251	1000 mg/L
3	May 4, 2020	120	122	121	
4	October 6, 2020	121	132	126.5	

Source: Primary data

4. CONCLUSION

While temperature and pH remained within safe limits, elevated BOD, COD, and TDS levels downstream suggest that hospital effluent contributes to organic and chemical loading in the Banong River.

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Strengthening wastewater treatment and implementing regular monitoring are essential to safeguard environmental and public health. A limitation of this study is that the results may vary depending on whether data is collected during the rainy or dry season. One way to address this is to collect data throughout the year (rainy and dry seasons) to capture full and even variability. A potential policy approach is data triangulation, using multiple methods or data sources (e.g., BMKG rainfall data, interviews, and field measurements) to validate the findings.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : **W**riting - **O**riginal Draft

E : **W**riting - **R**eview & **E**ditting

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

All authors state no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data supporting this study's findings are available from the corresponding author.

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